

Long-Term Care Quality Indicators for Older Adults in Low- and Middle-Income Countries

A Scoping Review Protocol

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Abstract

Long-term care (LTC) quality measurement remains underdeveloped in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where ageing populations strain fragmented systems without standardized indicators. Existing evidence draws heavily from high-income settings, limiting transferability to resource-constrained contexts like South Asia, sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America. To guide LTC indicator development, this scoping review will map structure, process, and outcome quality indicators for older adults from both global and LMIC sources, with emphasis on applicability to LMIC settings and identification of context-specific gaps. Following PRISMA-ScR guidelines, we will search MEDLINE via PubMed, Embase, and the Cochrane Library (2016–2026) using terms for LTC, quality indicators, and domains derived from the WHO Integrated Care for Older People (ICOPE) framework and WHO quality-of-care guidance for older adults. Grey literature from WHO IRIS, the World Bank Open Knowledge Repository, and Google Scholar (top 200 results by relevance) will supplement the database searches. Two reviewers will screen titles/abstracts and full texts against criteria: LTC settings for older adults, explicit/implicit quality indicators, and any empirical or literature-based study design (including quantitative, qualitative, mixed-methods studies, as well as reviews and reports). Data charting will capture indicator detail, mapped to the WHO Integrated Care for Older People (ICOPE) framework and WHO quality-of-care domains for older adults, including person-centredness, safety, effectiveness and continuity of care. Descriptive synthesis will present indicator matrices by domain and setting, highlighting LMIC examples and feasibility barriers across structure (workforce, organization of services), care processes (assessment, care planning, delivery of person-centered integrated care) and outcomes (functional ability, health status, satisfaction), with particular attention to LMIC gaps in workforce capacity and person-centered measures.

Background

The rapid ageing of the global population has made long-term care (LTC) an urgent policy and research priority. According to the United Nations, by 2050 one in six people worldwide will be over the age of 65, with the fastest growth occurring in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (United Nations, 2022). The World Health Organization stresses that ageing populations require health systems to adapt and invest in sustainable LTC models that safeguard dignity, independence, and quality of life (WHO, 2022). Population ageing is accelerating most rapidly in middle-income countries, where it is projected that approximately 71% of individuals aged 65 years and older will reside by 2050 (WHO, 2024). Women continue to constitute a larger proportion of the older population worldwide, reflecting consistently higher female life expectancy across all regions. Globally, life expectancy at birth increased from 66.8 years in 2000 to 73.3 years in 2019, while healthy life expectancy rose from 58.3 to 63.7 years over the same period. However, the difference between total life expectancy and healthy life expectancy widened from 8.5 to 9.6 years, indicating a growing period of life spent with illness or disability. This widening gap suggests an expansion of morbidity and a corresponding increase in the need for long-term care services (WHO, 2024).

In many low- and middle-income countries, rapid population ageing is transforming health and social care needs, while LTC systems remain fragmented and under-resourced. While traditionally older adults were cared for within extended families, rapid urbanization, migration, and changing family structures are eroding these systems (Jalal & Younis, 2014). With 2.1%, Pakistan is growing at a significantly higher rate than the other countries in South Asia (World Bank, 2020). Research highlights major gaps in geriatric care, including insufficient institutional capacity, limited geriatric training among healthcare professionals, and a lack of standardized approaches to quality measurement and improvement (Noreen et al., 2021; Jahan, 2016). The population is growing older and with life expectancy increasing steadily across LMICs, the burden of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and age-related loss of autonomy or disability is also rising (Kazibwe, Tran and Annerstedt, 2021). Recent research on trends in loss of autonomy among older adults in 23 LMICs indicates that the prevalence of severe activity limitations will change very little over the next 30 years; however, the absolute number of people experiencing such limitations will grow substantially as the older population expands (Weber and Scherbov, 2020). Thus, despite expected gains in life expectancy, the years spent in later life in poor health and without full autonomy are likely to increase. Meanwhile, there is mounting concern that family-based care of older persons alone—traditionally the cornerstone of old-age support and LTC—can no longer meet the escalating demand for LTC services in rapidly ageing LMICs (Feng, 2019).

To support countries in responding to population ageing, the United Nations has designated 2021–2030 as the Decade of Healthy Ageing, with the overarching goal of fostering healthy ageing and enhancing the well-being of older people. Among its key action areas is ensuring “access to long-term care for people who need it,” which is essential for older adults experiencing significant declines in physical or mental capacity to maintain functional ability and live with dignity and purpose. Baseline estimates suggest that over 142 million people aged 60 years and older—around 14% of the global 60+ population—are currently unable to meet all their basic daily needs because of functional limitations (WHO, 2020). Most of these older adults reside in low- and middle-income countries, where the absence of strong health and long-term care systems makes addressing their care needs especially challenging. Despite this growing evidence base, LTC quality measures for LMICs remain underdeveloped. Much of the international literature on quality in LTC is based on high-income country experiences (Zúñiga & Osińska 2020), which may not transfer easily to resource-constrained contexts.

This scoping review addresses this evidence gap by mapping existing LTC quality indicators and frameworks across global and LMIC contexts. It is the starting point for a larger project that will use these findings to inform subsequent studies on context-appropriate quality measurement. The review will chart indicators by domain—highlighting structural gaps like workforce shortages and facility readiness, process measures addressing care delivery and cultural appropriateness, and outcome indicators capturing resident well-being and family satisfaction. By identifying feasible, low-resource indicators and adaptation barriers, this phase establishes the evidence foundation for subsequent studies, directly informing context-

appropriate quality measurement for resource-constrained systems.

Rationale

Long-term care (LTC) systems in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) face escalating demands from rapid ageing, yet lack standardized quality indicators tailored to resource constraints, fragmented services, and cultural contexts. Existing literature predominantly reflects high-income country experiences, where advanced infrastructure and data systems enable the routine collection of detailed quality measures that often prove infeasible in LMIC settings characterized by workforce shortages, weak routine data, and reliance on family or informal providers. A scoping review is essential to comprehensively map the breadth of existing LTC quality indicators—structure (e.g., staffing, facilities), process (e.g., care delivery, person-centered practices), and outcome (e.g., resident health, satisfaction) across global and LMIC contexts.

Aim

To map existing structure, process, and outcome quality indicators for long-term care (LTC) of older adults across global and LMIC contexts, organizing them using the WHO Integrated Care for Older People (ICOPE) framework and WHO quality-of-care domains.

Specific objectives

1. Chart the range of LTC quality indicators for older adults, organizing them according to domains derived from the WHO Integrated Care for Older People (ICOPE) framework and WHO quality-of-care guidance, using published studies and grey literature (2016–2026).
2. Describe indicator characteristics (data sources, psychometrics, country contexts), including the distribution of indicators by LMIC.
3. Identify barriers and enablers for the implementation and feasibility in fragmented LTC landscape in LMIC.
4. Generate a consolidated long-list of candidate domains and indicators, prioritized for feasibility and relevance in LMIC settings.

Methodology

Protocol and registration

This scoping review protocol follows the PRISMA-ScR guidelines and the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews (Peters et al., 2020). The complete protocol will be prospectively registered on Zenodo prior to commencing database searches, ensuring transparency and reducing duplication risk. Protocol amendments will be tracked with version dates and justifications. Version 1.1, deposited 2026-06-05: corrects field-tag inconsistencies in the PubMed and Cochrane Setting blocks; revises the WB OKR and Google Scholar grey-literature search strings for platform compatibility; removes the hand-search of reference lists from the grey-literature strategy; adds the Department of Public Health affiliation; minor copy-edit corrections.

Search strategy

We will search MEDLINE via PubMed, Embase, and the Cochrane Library. To identify recent studies not yet indexed, we will additionally search Google Scholar. Search terms will combine two concepts at the database level: (1) long-term care settings for older adults and (2) low- and middle-income country (LMIC) contexts. For each concept, we will use a combination of controlled vocabulary and free-text terms restricted to title, abstract, and keyword fields. Setting terms include nursing home, care home, residential care, assisted living, long-term care, home for the aged, skilled nursing, and aged care, supported by MeSH headings (e.g., "Nursing Homes", "Homes for the Aged", "Long-Term Care") and Emtree descriptors (e.g., V1.1

'nursing home'/de, 'long term care'/de). LMIC terms include developing countries, low- and middle-income countries, resource-limited settings, global south, and an explicit list of all LMICs as classified by the World Bank, supported by MeSH headings such as "Developing Countries" and Emtree terms such as 'developing country'/exp. To balance precision against recall, selected broad subject headings will be applied without explosion (no-exp / /de) so as not to import overly narrow descendant terms (e.g., "Nursing Homes"[MeSH:NoExp] in PubMed; 'nursing home'/de in Embase). Cochrane Library searches rely on free-text terms with field tags (:ti,ab,kw) and the NEXT proximity operator for wildcarded phrases (e.g., developing NEXT countr*), since the Cochrane Library is a heterogeneous source and MeSH tagging is incomplete across its constituent records. Truncation (*) and wildcards will be applied where supported by each interface. No language restrictions will be imposed; non-English records will be machine-translated as needed at the screening stage. The complete database-specific search strategies, including final Boolean syntax for each block, are reported in Appendix A. Findings will be supplemented through targeted searches of WHO IRIS, the World Bank Open Knowledge Repository, and the first 200 results of Google Scholar (Appendix A2). The full strategy was developed in consultation with a medical librarian and will be pilot-tested and peer-reviewed (PRESS checklist) prior to execution.

Eligibility criteria (PCC Framework for Scoping Review)

Inclusion Criteria:

- Population: Older adults (≥60 years) receiving any form of long-term care services
- Concept: Quality indicators, performance measures, quality metrics, or frameworks explicitly or implicitly using Donabedian domains (structure, process, outcome)
- Context: Any LTC setting (institutional, residential, home-based, hospital long-stay units)
- Types of sources: Peer-reviewed studies, systematic/scoping reviews, quality reports, theses, conference papers, policy documents, guidelines, WHO/World Bank grey literature
- Date range: 2016–2026
- Language: All languages (machine translation for non-English)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Acute hospital without LTC component
- Pediatric or working-age populations
- Patient or family satisfaction studies that do not report specific, measurable indicators or metrics (e.g., only open-ended narratives without defined items or scales. Satisfaction studies without specific indicators or metrics)
- Theoretical papers without practical, measurable indicators
- Pre-2016 publications

Source selection (screening)

All identified records will be exported from the three databases and imported into Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia) for de-duplication and screening. Duplicates will be removed automatically by Covidence with manual verification of borderline matches. Screening will proceed in two stages: (i) title and abstract screening against the inclusion and exclusion criteria above, and (ii) full-text review of all records advanced from stage 1. Reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage will be recorded and reported in the PRISMA-ScR flow diagram.

Two reviewers will independently conduct screening: NA (Reviewer 1) and CS (Reviewer 2), in line with the JBI requirement for dual-reviewer screening in scoping reviews (Peters et al., 2020). A calibration exercise will be performed on the first 20 records at each stage, after which NA and CS will meet to compare decisions, resolve discrepancies, and refine the operational application of the eligibility criteria. The remaining records will be split between the two reviewers, with a planned overlap subset of approximately 10 % screened in duplicate to monitor inter-rater agreement throughout.

Disagreements between NA and CS at either screening stage will be resolved by discussion in the first

instance. Persisting disagreements will be escalated to Prof. Dr. MS (Reviewer 3) for adjudication.

Data extraction and management

Data extraction and management will follow JBI scoping review methodology using a standardized charting form developed in Microsoft Excel and pilot-tested on 10 included sources to ensure consistency and completeness. The form will capture core bibliographic details (author, year, title, DOI), study characteristics (country income level, LTC setting, population age/comorbidities), and detailed indicator information, including classification by service inputs/organization, care processes, and outcomes aligned with WHO's Integrated Care for Older People (ICOPE) framework and WHO quality-of-care domains for older adults. For each indicator, we will record the indicator name and description, data sources (records, surveys, observations), numerator/denominator formulas, psychometric properties (reliability, validity), and feasibility considerations (time, cost, training requirements, prior LMIC testing). Additional qualitative fields will document barriers and enablers for LMIC adaptation, cultural considerations, and author recommendations. Two reviewers will independently extract data from the first 20 sources, meet to compare results and refine the form, then proceed with a single extraction for the remaining sources, verified through 10% random double-checking. Authors will be contacted for critical missing data such as calculation formulas. All data will be stored in Excel files on the server of the University of Basel.

Synthesis will involve descriptive frequency analysis of indicators by ICOPE/WHO QoC domain grouping, LTC setting, and country income level, presented through structured indicator matrices and visual heat maps showing LMIC coverage gaps. Narrative synthesis will highlight common feasibility barriers (workforce constraints, data infrastructure limitations) and an exemplary adaptation pathway for Pakistan's fragmented LTC context. No meta-analysis or formal quality appraisal will be conducted, in line with scoping review standards. The process targets completion within Month 4 post-screening, yielding a consolidated long-list of indicators organized by ICOPE/WHO QoC domains for the subsequent study.

Data synthesis

Data synthesis will follow Joanna Briggs Institute scoping review methodology using descriptive numerical analysis and narrative synthesis without meta-analysis, statistical pooling, or quality appraisal of individual studies. Numerical data will be summarized through frequencies and proportions characterizing the nature and distribution of included sources and quality indicators, including counts by publication year, and country income level (high-, upper-middle-, lower-middle-, and low-income), categorized according to the World Bank classification, long-term care setting (institutional, residential, home-based, hospital long-stay), and study design.

Indicators will be grouped according to domains derived from the WHO Integrated Care for Older People (ICOPE) framework, WHO quality-of-care dimensions for older adults, and any additional cross-cutting domains that emerge from the data (e.g., governance, financing), with geographic coverage analysis highlighting high-income country versus LMIC representation and South Asian examples. Data source utilization will be quantified by distinguishing routine records, surveys, observations, and administrative data systems.

The core synthesis product will comprise structured indicator matrices presenting candidate indicators organized by ICOPE/WHO QoC and emergent domains in tabular format, capturing indicator name, description, data source, numerator/denominator formula, psychometric properties, prior LMIC testing, and feasibility considerations (training requirements, cost, time burden). Visualizations will include a PRISMA-ScR flow diagram, bar charts displaying indicator distribution by domain, and heat maps illustrating coverage by country income level and LTC setting.

Narrative synthesis will thematically analyze extraction notes addressing feasibility patterns across resource contexts, common methodological limitations, measurement challenges (psychometrics, risk adjustment), and an exemplary adaptation pathway for Pakistan's fragmented public-private-charity LTC landscape. Indicators will be qualitatively categorized by LMIC feasibility (high: routine data/minimal training; medium: surveys/moderate training; low: complex calculations/specialist equipment). Knowledge gaps will be explicitly mapped, including understudied and emergent domains (e.g., cultural

appropriateness, family caregiving, social participation), key populations (e.g., dementia, rural setting), and implementation evidence.

Results will be presented through consolidated Excel matrices available as supplementary material, yielding a prioritized long list of candidate indicators for the study.

Ethical consideration

No ethical approval is needed for this type of study. We will only use data from previously published studies or reports.

Funding

None.

Dissemination

Results from this scoping review will be disseminated through multiple channels to maximize academic, policy, and practice impact. The primary output will be a peer-reviewed publication. Secondary dissemination will target diverse audiences through conference presentations.

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Appendix A

Search Strategies (PubMed-MEDLINE, Embase, Cochrane Library | 2016–2026)

A1. Database Search Strings Table

	Block	Search Terms
PubMed-MEDLINE	#1 Setting	"Nursing Homes"[MeSH:NoExp] OR "Homes for the Aged"[MeSH] OR "Nursing Home Residents"[MeSH] OR "Long-Term Care"[MeSH] OR "Residential Facilities"[MeSH:NoExp] OR "Assisted Living Facilities"[MeSH] OR "nursing home"[tiab] OR "nursing homes"[tiab] OR "care home"[tiab] OR "care homes"[tiab] OR "old age home"[tiab] OR "old age homes"[tiab] OR "aged care"[tiab] OR "skilled nursing"[tiab] OR "long-term care"[tiab] OR "long term care"[tiab] OR "elderly care"[tiab] OR "geriatric care"[tiab] OR "residential care"[tiab] OR "institutional care"[tiab]
	#2 LMICs	("Developing Countries"[Mesh] OR "Africa"[Mesh] OR "Latin America"[Mesh] OR "Indian Ocean Islands"[Mesh] OR "Pacific Islands"[Mesh] OR "developing countr*" [tiab] OR "developing nation*" [tiab] OR "developing world"[tiab] OR "less developed countr*" [tiab] OR "less-developed countr*" [tiab] OR "under developed countr*" [tiab] OR "underdeveloped countr*" [tiab] OR "least developed countr*" [tiab] OR "low income countr*" [tiab] OR "low-income countr*" [tiab] OR "lower income countr*" [tiab] OR "lower-income countr*" [tiab] OR "middle income countr*" [tiab] OR "middle-income countr*" [tiab] OR "lower middle income"[tiab] OR "lower-middle-income"[tiab] OR "upper middle income"[tiab] OR "upper-middle-income"[tiab] OR "low and middle income"[tiab] OR "low- and middle-income"[tiab] OR "low or middle income"[tiab] OR "third world"[tiab] OR "transitional countr*" [tiab] OR "emerging econom*" [tiab] OR "emerging market*" [tiab] OR "newly industrial*" [tiab] OR "global south"[tiab] OR LMIC[tiab] OR LMICs[tiab] OR LIC[tiab] OR LICs[tiab] OR "resource limited"[tiab] OR "resource-limited"[tiab] OR "resource poor"[tiab] OR "resource-poor"[tiab] OR "resource constrained"[tiab] OR "resource-constrained"[tiab] OR "low resource"[tiab] OR "low-resource"[tiab] OR Afghanistan[tiab] OR Albania[tiab] OR Algeria[tiab] OR Angola[tiab] OR Argentina[tiab] OR Armenia[tiab] OR Azerbaijan[tiab] OR Bangladesh[tiab] OR Belarus[tiab] OR Belize[tiab] OR Benin[tiab] OR Bhutan[tiab] OR Bolivia[tiab] OR "Bosnia and Herzegovina"[tiab] OR Bosnia[tiab] OR Herzegovina[tiab] OR Botswana[tiab] OR Brazil[tiab] OR Bulgaria[tiab] OR "Burkina Faso"[tiab] OR "Upper Volta"[tiab] OR Burundi[tiab] OR "Cabo Verde"[tiab] OR "Cape Verde"[tiab] OR Cambodia[tiab] OR Kampuchea[tiab] OR Cameroon[tiab] OR "Central African Republic"[tiab] OR Chad[tiab] OR China[tiab] OR Colombia[tiab] OR Comoros[tiab] OR Congo[tiab] OR Zaire[tiab] OR "Costa Rica"[tiab] OR "Cote d'Ivoire"[tiab] OR "Ivory Coast"[tiab] OR Cuba[tiab] OR Djibouti[tiab] OR Dominica[tiab] OR "Dominican Republic"[tiab] OR Ecuador[tiab] OR Egypt[tiab] OR "El Salvador"[tiab] OR "Equatorial Guinea"[tiab] OR Eritrea[tiab] OR Eswatini[tiab] OR Swaziland[tiab] OR Ethiopia[tiab] OR Fiji[tiab] OR Gabon[tiab] OR Gambia[tiab] OR Ghana[tiab] OR Grenada[tiab] OR Guatemala[tiab] OR Guinea[tiab] OR "Guinea-Bissau"[tiab] OR Guyana[tiab] OR Haiti[tiab] OR Honduras[tiab] OR India[tiab] OR Indonesia[tiab] OR Iran[tiab] OR Persia[tiab] OR Iraq[tiab] OR Jamaica[tiab] OR Jordan[tiab] OR Kazakhstan[tiab] OR Kenya[tiab] OR Kiribati[tiab] OR Kosovo[tiab] OR Kyrgyzstan[tiab] OR "Kyrgyz Republic"[tiab] OR Laos[tiab] OR "Lao PDR"[tiab] OR Lebanon[tiab] OR Lesotho[tiab] OR Liberia[tiab] OR Libya[tiab] OR Madagascar[tiab] OR Malawi[tiab] OR Malaysia[tiab] OR Maldives[tiab] OR Mali[tiab] OR "Marshall Islands"[tiab] OR Mauritania[tiab] OR Mauritius[tiab] OR Mexico[tiab] OR Micronesia[tiab] OR Moldova[tiab] OR Mongolia[tiab] OR Montenegro[tiab] OR Morocco[tiab] OR Mozambique[tiab] OR Myanmar[tiab] OR Burma[tiab] OR Namibia[tiab] OR Nepal[tiab] OR Nicaragua[tiab] OR Niger[tiab] OR Nigeria[tiab] OR "North Korea"[tiab] OR "Democratic People's Republic of Korea"[tiab] OR DPRK[tiab] OR "North Macedonia"[tiab] OR Macedonia[tiab] OR Pakistan[tiab] OR Palau[tiab] OR Palestine[tiab] OR "West Bank"[tiab] OR Gaza[tiab] OR "Papua New Guinea"[tiab] OR Paraguay[tiab] OR Peru[tiab] OR Philippines[tiab] OR Romania[tiab] OR Russia[tiab] OR "Russian Federation"[tiab] OR Rwanda[tiab] OR Samoa[tiab] OR "Sao Tome"[tiab]

		OR Senegal[tiab] OR Serbia[tiab] OR "Sierra Leone"[tiab] OR "Solomon Islands"[tiab] OR Somalia[tiab] OR "South Africa"[tiab] OR "South Sudan"[tiab] OR "Sri Lanka"[tiab] OR Ceylon[tiab] OR "Saint Lucia"[tiab] OR "St Lucia"[tiab] OR "Saint Vincent"[tiab] OR "St Vincent"[tiab] OR Sudan[tiab] OR Suriname[tiab] OR Syria[tiab] OR Tajikistan[tiab] OR Tanzania[tiab] OR Thailand[tiab] OR Siam[tiab] OR "Timor-Leste"[tiab] OR "East Timor"[tiab] OR Togo[tiab] OR Tonga[tiab] OR Tunisia[tiab] OR Turkey[tiab] OR Türkiye[tiab] OR Turkmenistan[tiab] OR Tuvalu[tiab] OR Uganda[tiab] OR Ukraine[tiab] OR Uzbekistan[tiab] OR Vanuatu[tiab] OR Venezuela[tiab] OR Vietnam[tiab] OR "Viet Nam"[tiab] OR Yemen[tiab] OR Zambia[tiab] OR Zimbabwe[tiab] OR Rhodesia[tiab] OR "sub-Saharan Africa"[tiab] OR "subsaharan Africa"[tiab] OR "Latin America"[tiab] OR Caribbean[tiab] OR "South Asia"[tiab] OR "Southeast Asia"[tiab] OR "South-East Asia"[tiab] OR "Central Asia"[tiab] OR "Middle East"[tiab])
EMBASE	#1 Setting	('nursing home'/de OR 'home for the aged'/de OR 'nursing home patient'/de OR 'long term care'/de OR 'residential care'/de OR 'assisted living facility'/de OR 'nursing home':ti,ab OR 'nursing homes':ti,ab OR 'care home':ti,ab OR 'care homes':ti,ab OR 'old age home':ti,ab OR 'old age homes':ti,ab OR 'aged care':ti,ab OR 'elderly care':ti,ab OR 'geriatric care':ti,ab OR 'skilled nursing':ti,ab OR 'long-term care':ti,ab OR 'long term care':ti,ab OR 'residential care':ti,ab OR 'institutional care':ti,ab OR 'assisted living':ti,ab)
	#2 LMICs	('developing country'/exp OR 'africa'/exp OR 'south america'/exp OR 'central america'/exp OR 'caribbean'/exp OR 'pacific islands'/exp OR 'developing country':ti,ab OR 'developing countries':ti,ab OR 'developing nation':ti,ab OR 'developing nations':ti,ab OR 'developing world':ti,ab OR 'less developed':ti,ab OR 'less developed countries':ti,ab OR 'less-developed countries':ti,ab OR 'under developed':ti,ab OR 'under-developed':ti,ab OR 'underdeveloped':ti,ab OR 'least developed':ti,ab OR 'least developed countries':ti,ab OR 'low income':ti,ab OR 'low-income':ti,ab OR 'low income country':ti,ab OR 'low income countries':ti,ab OR 'low-income countries':ti,ab OR 'lower income':ti,ab OR 'lower-income':ti,ab OR 'middle income':ti,ab OR 'middle-income':ti,ab OR 'middle income country':ti,ab OR 'middle income countries':ti,ab OR 'middle-income countries':ti,ab OR 'low and middle income':ti,ab OR 'low- and middle-income':ti,ab OR 'low or middle income':ti,ab OR 'lower middle income':ti,ab OR 'lower-middle-income':ti,ab OR 'upper middle income':ti,ab OR 'upper-middle-income':ti,ab OR 'third world':ti,ab OR 'transitional country':ti,ab OR 'transitional countries':ti,ab OR 'emerging economy':ti,ab OR 'emerging economies':ti,ab OR 'emerging market':ti,ab OR 'emerging markets':ti,ab OR 'newly industrialized':ti,ab OR 'newly industrialised':ti,ab OR 'global south':ti,ab OR 'lic':ti,ab OR 'lics':ti,ab OR 'resource limited':ti,ab OR 'resource-limited':ti,ab OR 'resource poor':ti,ab OR 'resource-poor':ti,ab OR 'resource constrained':ti,ab OR 'resource-constrained':ti,ab OR 'low resource':ti,ab OR 'low-resource':ti,ab OR afghanistan:ti,ab OR albania:ti,ab OR algeria:ti,ab OR angola:ti,ab OR argentina:ti,ab OR armenia:ti,ab OR azerbaijan:ti,ab OR bangladesh:ti,ab OR belarus:ti,ab OR belize:ti,ab OR benin:ti,ab OR bhutan:ti,ab OR bolivia:ti,ab OR 'bosnia and herzegovina':ti,ab OR bosnia:ti,ab OR herzegovina:ti,ab OR botswana:ti,ab OR brazil:ti,ab OR bulgaria:ti,ab OR 'burkina faso':ti,ab OR 'upper volta':ti,ab OR burundi:ti,ab OR 'cabo verde':ti,ab OR 'cape verde':ti,ab OR cambodia:ti,ab OR kampuchea:ti,ab OR cameroon:ti,ab OR 'central african republic':ti,ab OR chad:ti,ab OR china:ti,ab OR colombia:ti,ab OR comoros:ti,ab OR congo:ti,ab OR zaire:ti,ab OR 'costa rica':ti,ab OR 'ivory coast':ti,ab OR cuba:ti,ab OR djibouti:ti,ab OR dominica:ti,ab OR 'dominican republic':ti,ab OR ecuador:ti,ab OR egypt:ti,ab OR 'el salvador':ti,ab OR 'equatorial guinea':ti,ab OR eritrea:ti,ab OR eswatini:ti,ab OR swaziland:ti,ab OR ethiopia:ti,ab OR fiji:ti,ab OR gabon:ti,ab OR gambia:ti,ab OR georgia:ti,ab OR ghana:ti,ab OR grenada:ti,ab OR guatemala:ti,ab OR guinea:ti,ab OR 'guinea-bissau':ti,ab OR guyana:ti,ab OR haiti:ti,ab OR honduras:ti,ab OR india:ti,ab OR indonesia:ti,ab OR iran:ti,ab OR persia:ti,ab OR iraq:ti,ab OR jamaica:ti,ab OR jordan:ti,ab OR kazakhstan:ti,ab OR kenya:ti,ab OR kiribati:ti,ab OR kosovo:ti,ab OR kyrgyzstan:ti,ab OR 'kyrgyz republic':ti,ab OR laos:ti,ab OR 'lao pdr':ti,ab OR lebanon:ti,ab OR lesotho:ti,ab OR liberia:ti,ab OR libya:ti,ab OR madagascar:ti,ab OR malawi:ti,ab OR

		malaysia:ti,ab OR maldives:ti,ab OR mali:ti,ab OR 'marshall islands':ti,ab OR mauritania:ti,ab OR mauritius:ti,ab OR mexico:ti,ab OR micronesia:ti,ab OR moldova:ti,ab OR mongolia:ti,ab OR montenegro:ti,ab OR morocco:ti,ab OR mozambique:ti,ab OR myanmar:ti,ab OR burma:ti,ab OR namibia:ti,ab OR nepal:ti,ab OR nicaragua:ti,ab OR niger:ti,ab OR nigeria:ti,ab OR 'north korea':ti,ab OR dprk:ti,ab OR 'north macedonia':ti,ab OR macedonia:ti,ab OR pakistan:ti,ab OR palau:ti,ab OR palestine:ti,ab OR 'west bank':ti,ab OR gaza:ti,ab OR 'papua new guinea':ti,ab OR paraguay:ti,ab OR peru:ti,ab OR philippines:ti,ab OR romania:ti,ab OR russia:ti,ab OR 'russian federation':ti,ab OR rwanda:ti,ab OR samoa:ti,ab OR 'sao tome':ti,ab OR senegal:ti,ab OR serbia:ti,ab OR 'sierra leone':ti,ab OR 'solomon islands':ti,ab OR somalia:ti,ab OR 'south africa':ti,ab OR 'south sudan':ti,ab OR 'sri lanka':ti,ab OR ceylon:ti,ab OR 'saint lucia':ti,ab OR 'st lucia':ti,ab OR 'saint vincent':ti,ab OR 'st vincent':ti,ab OR sudan:ti,ab OR suriname:ti,ab OR syria:ti,ab OR tajikistan:ti,ab OR tanzania:ti,ab OR thailand:ti,ab OR siam:ti,ab OR 'timor-leste':ti,ab OR 'east timor':ti,ab OR togo:ti,ab OR tonga:ti,ab OR tunisia:ti,ab OR turkey:ti,ab OR turkmenistan:ti,ab OR tuvalu:ti,ab OR uganda:ti,ab OR ukraine:ti,ab OR uzbekistan:ti,ab OR vanuatu:ti,ab OR venezuela:ti,ab OR vietnam:ti,ab OR 'viet nam':ti,ab OR yemen:ti,ab OR zambia:ti,ab OR zimbabwe:ti,ab OR rhodesia:ti,ab OR 'sub-saharan africa':ti,ab OR 'subsaharan africa':ti,ab OR 'latin america':ti,ab OR caribbean:ti,ab OR 'south asia':ti,ab OR 'southeast asia':ti,ab OR 'south-east asia':ti,ab OR 'central asia':ti,ab OR 'middle east':ti,ab)
Cochrane Library	#1 Setting	"nursing home":ti,ab,kw OR "nursing homes":ti,ab,kw OR "care home":ti,ab,kw OR "care homes":ti,ab,kw OR "old age home":ti,ab,kw OR "old age homes":ti,ab,kw OR "aged care":ti,ab,kw OR "skilled nursing":ti,ab,kw OR "long-term care":ti,ab,kw OR "long term care":ti,ab,kw OR "home for the aged":ti,ab,kw OR "homes for the aged":ti,ab,kw OR "assisted living":ti,ab,kw OR (nursing NEXT home NEXT resident*):ti,ab,kw OR "elderly care":ti,ab,kw OR "geriatric care":ti,ab,kw OR "residential care":ti,ab,kw OR "institutional care":ti,ab,kw
	#2 LMICs	(developing NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (developing NEXT nation*):ti,ab,kw OR "developing world":ti,ab,kw OR (less NEXT developed NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (under NEXT developed NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (underdeveloped NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (least NEXT developed NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (low NEXT income NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (lower NEXT income NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (middle NEXT income NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR "lower middle income":ti,ab,kw OR "upper middle income":ti,ab,kw OR "low and middle income":ti,ab,kw OR "low or middle income":ti,ab,kw OR "third world":ti,ab,kw OR (transitional NEXT countr*):ti,ab,kw OR (emerging NEXT econom*):ti,ab,kw OR (emerging NEXT market*):ti,ab,kw OR (newly NEXT industrial*):ti,ab,kw OR "global south":ti,ab,kw OR LMIC:ti,ab,kw OR LMICs:ti,ab,kw OR LIC:ti,ab,kw OR LICs:ti,ab,kw OR "resource limited":ti,ab,kw OR "resource poor":ti,ab,kw OR "resource constrained":ti,ab,kw OR "low resource":ti,ab,kw OR "Pacific Islands":ti,ab,kw OR "Indian Ocean Islands":ti,ab,kw OR Afghanistan:ti,ab,kw OR Albania:ti,ab,kw OR Algeria:ti,ab,kw OR Angola:ti,ab,kw OR Argentina:ti,ab,kw OR Armenia:ti,ab,kw OR Azerbaijan:ti,ab,kw OR Bangladesh:ti,ab,kw OR Belarus:ti,ab,kw OR Belize:ti,ab,kw OR Benin:ti,ab,kw OR Bhutan:ti,ab,kw OR Bolivia:ti,ab,kw OR "Bosnia and Herzegovina":ti,ab,kw OR Bosnia:ti,ab,kw OR Herzegovina:ti,ab,kw OR Botswana:ti,ab,kw OR Brazil:ti,ab,kw OR Bulgaria:ti,ab,kw OR "Burkina Faso":ti,ab,kw OR "Upper Volta":ti,ab,kw OR Burundi:ti,ab,kw OR "Cabo Verde":ti,ab,kw OR "Cape Verde":ti,ab,kw OR Cambodia:ti,ab,kw OR Kampuchea:ti,ab,kw OR Cameroon:ti,ab,kw OR "Central African Republic":ti,ab,kw OR Chad:ti,ab,kw OR China:ti,ab,kw OR Colombia:ti,ab,kw OR Comoros:ti,ab,kw OR Congo:ti,ab,kw OR Zaire:ti,ab,kw OR "Costa Rica":ti,ab,kw OR "Cote d'Ivoire":ti,ab,kw OR "Ivory Coast":ti,ab,kw OR Cuba:ti,ab,kw OR Djibouti:ti,ab,kw OR Dominica:ti,ab,kw OR "Dominican Republic":ti,ab,kw OR Ecuador:ti,ab,kw OR Egypt:ti,ab,kw OR "El Salvador":ti,ab,kw OR "Equatorial Guinea":ti,ab,kw OR Eritrea:ti,ab,kw OR Eswatini:ti,ab,kw OR Swaziland:ti,ab,kw OR Ethiopia:ti,ab,kw OR Fiji:ti,ab,kw OR Gabon:ti,ab,kw OR Gambia:ti,ab,kw OR Ghana:ti,ab,kw OR Grenada:ti,ab,kw OR Guatemala:ti,ab,kw OR Guinea:ti,ab,kw OR "Guinea-Bissau":ti,ab,kw OR Guyana:ti,ab,kw OR Haiti:ti,ab,kw OR Honduras:ti,ab,kw OR India:ti,ab,kw

	<p>OR Indonesia:ti,ab,kw OR Iran:ti,ab,kw OR Persia:ti,ab,kw OR Iraq:ti,ab,kw OR Jamaica:ti,ab,kw OR Jordan:ti,ab,kw OR Kazakhstan:ti,ab,kw OR Kenya:ti,ab,kw OR Kiribati:ti,ab,kw OR Kosovo:ti,ab,kw OR Kyrgyzstan:ti,ab,kw OR "Kyrgyz Republic":ti,ab,kw OR Laos:ti,ab,kw OR "Lao PDR":ti,ab,kw OR Lebanon:ti,ab,kw OR Lesotho:ti,ab,kw OR Liberia:ti,ab,kw OR Libya:ti,ab,kw OR Madagascar:ti,ab,kw OR Malawi:ti,ab,kw OR Malaysia:ti,ab,kw OR Maldives:ti,ab,kw OR Mali:ti,ab,kw OR "Marshall Islands":ti,ab,kw OR Mauritania:ti,ab,kw OR Mauritius:ti,ab,kw OR Mexico:ti,ab,kw OR Micronesia:ti,ab,kw OR Moldova:ti,ab,kw OR Mongolia:ti,ab,kw OR Montenegro:ti,ab,kw OR Morocco:ti,ab,kw OR Mozambique:ti,ab,kw OR Myanmar:ti,ab,kw OR Burma:ti,ab,kw OR Namibia:ti,ab,kw OR Nepal:ti,ab,kw OR Nicaragua:ti,ab,kw OR Niger:ti,ab,kw OR Nigeria:ti,ab,kw OR "North Korea":ti,ab,kw OR "Democratic People's Republic of Korea":ti,ab,kw OR DPRK:ti,ab,kw OR "North Macedonia":ti,ab,kw OR Macedonia:ti,ab,kw OR Pakistan:ti,ab,kw OR Palau:ti,ab,kw OR Palestine:ti,ab,kw OR "West Bank":ti,ab,kw OR Gaza:ti,ab,kw OR "Papua New Guinea":ti,ab,kw OR Paraguay:ti,ab,kw OR Peru:ti,ab,kw OR Philippines:ti,ab,kw OR Romania:ti,ab,kw OR Russia:ti,ab,kw OR "Russian Federation":ti,ab,kw OR Rwanda:ti,ab,kw OR Samoa:ti,ab,kw OR "Sao Tome":ti,ab,kw OR Senegal:ti,ab,kw OR Serbia:ti,ab,kw OR "Sierra Leone":ti,ab,kw OR "Solomon Islands":ti,ab,kw OR Somalia:ti,ab,kw OR "South Africa":ti,ab,kw OR "South Sudan":ti,ab,kw OR "Sri Lanka":ti,ab,kw OR Ceylon:ti,ab,kw OR "Saint Lucia":ti,ab,kw OR "St Lucia":ti,ab,kw OR "Saint Vincent":ti,ab,kw OR "St Vincent":ti,ab,kw OR Sudan:ti,ab,kw OR Suriname:ti,ab,kw OR Syria:ti,ab,kw OR Tajikistan:ti,ab,kw OR Tanzania:ti,ab,kw OR Thailand:ti,ab,kw OR Siam:ti,ab,kw OR "Timor-Leste":ti,ab,kw OR "East Timor":ti,ab,kw OR Togo:ti,ab,kw OR Tonga:ti,ab,kw OR Tunisia:ti,ab,kw OR Turkey:ti,ab,kw OR Türkiye:ti,ab,kw OR Turkmenistan:ti,ab,kw OR Tuvalu:ti,ab,kw OR Uganda:ti,ab,kw OR Ukraine:ti,ab,kw OR Uzbekistan:ti,ab,kw OR Vanuatu:ti,ab,kw OR Venezuela:ti,ab,kw OR Vietnam:ti,ab,kw OR "Viet Nam":ti,ab,kw OR Yemen:ti,ab,kw OR Zambia:ti,ab,kw OR Zimbabwe:ti,ab,kw OR Rhodesia:ti,ab,kw OR "sub-Saharan Africa":ti,ab,kw OR "subsaharan Africa":ti,ab,kw OR "Latin America":ti,ab,kw OR Caribbean:ti,ab,kw OR "South Asia":ti,ab,kw OR "Southeast Asia":ti,ab,kw OR "South-East Asia":ti,ab,kw OR "Central Asia":ti,ab,kw OR "Middle East":ti,ab,kw</p>
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A2. Grey Literature Sources Table (2016-2026)

Source	Search Terms
WHO IRIS	"long-term care" AND quality AND indicators AND (older OR ageing)
World Bank Open Knowledge	(elderly OR "older people") AND ("long-term care" OR "nursing home") AND quality
Google Scholar	LTC quality indicators LMIC (older OR ageing)